

susceptibility in 1988 at RARS, Jagtial, and surrounding villages.

High GM incidence was observed in multilocation varietal trials during 1992 WS in Siam 29 derivatives Phalguna, Surekha, WGL 3962, and WGL 3943. Eswarakora derivatives were resistant (Table 2).

Phalguna, Surekha, and ARC5984, differentials derived from Siam 29 and belonging to group II, were susceptible to the local GM population in Karimnagar District in 1992-93, indicating a change in the pattern of reaction from biotype 1 to one similar to that of biotype 3. ■

Field screening of rice cultivars for resistance to gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* in coastal Karnataka, India

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Gall midge (GM) is increasing in incidence in the coastal region of Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka State. We screened 50 promising cultures for resistance during 1992-93 wet seasons (WS).

Cultures were transplanted in 4-m rows spaced at 20 cm. We recorded the number of tillers and percentage showing silvershoots 50 d after transplanting for 10 randomly selected hills per row. Ten entries were resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to GM infestation in the field, Karnataka, India, 1992-93 WS.

Av silvershoots (%)	Lines
0-5	IET9691, IET11475, IET12179, IET12351, IET12797, IET12811, IR36, Abhaya, Suraksha, Shakthi
5-10	IET9683, IET10851, IET10318, IET11151, IET11375, IET11467, IET12186, IET12187, IET12188, IET12191, IET12419, H4, Sasyasree, Kasturi, Pusa Basmati 1, Jaldi 2, Jaldi 3
10-20	IET9553, IET10265, IET10720, IET11466, IET12183, IET12190, Jaldi 1, Jaldi 4, PNR162, PNR166, PNR519, PNR546, PNR381, IR22 (R), Ratna, Vibhava, Vikas, Mangala, Rasi
20 or more	Sonasali, Avinash, IR20, Jaya (check)

Stress tolerance

Response of rice plants from different regions to ultraviolet-B radiation

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Increased ultraviolet-B (UV-B) radiation (280-320 nm), as a result of stratospheric ozone depletion, has damaging effects on several plant physiological processes including photosynthesis, carbohydrate status, ion uptake, and ultimately, dry matter production. Species and varietal differences, in terms of sensitivity to enhanced UV-B, have been reported. Varietal differences have been noted in rice. It is possible that land races and cultivars originating from high UV-B areas have greater tolerance.

We tested the hypothesis that rice cultivars originating from regions with higher ambient UV-B radiation are more tolerant of UV-B radiation by evaluating their growth response to elevated UV-B radiation.

We screened 188 rice cultivars from various varietal groups and ecosystems, supplied by the International Rice

Number of rice cultivars in a group showing a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) in plant height, tiller number, leaf area, and dry weight when exposed to 3 wk of enhanced UV-B radiation.

Group	Number of cultivars	Plant height	Tiller number	Leaf area	Dry weight
Indica	117	87 (74) ^a	26 (22)	39 (33)	40 (34)
Japonica ^b	55	42 (76)	8 (15)	15 (27)	13 (24)
Javanica ^b	7	5 (71)	5 (71)	3 (43)	3 (43)
Hybrid	9	9 (100)	2 (25)	5 (73)	5 (73)
Total	188	143 (76)	41 (22)	62 (28)	61 (32)

^aValues in parentheses represent the percentage of cultivars affected. ^bJaponica and javanica groups do not differ by isozyme analysis.

Germplasm Center at IRRI, for their growth response to UV-B treatment from 1991 to 1992. Cultivars were screened in batches of 22. Seeds were pregerminated at 30 °C for 24 h and then sown in 1-liter plastic pots containing 1.7 kg of Maahas clay soil fertilized with 0.4 g N, 0.04 g P, and 0.25 g K/kg soil.

Plants were grown in the greenhouse for 10 d and then subjected to UV-B treatment for 3 wk in a temperature- and humidity-controlled glasshouse (day/night temperature = 27/21 °C; relative humidity = 70%). UV-emitting fluorescent lamps supplied the UV-B radiation. Plants were irradiated for 6 h/d

(0900-1500 h). The average biologically effective UV-B radiation ($UV-B_{BE}$) was 13.0 kJ/m² per d. Six plants (2 pots) from each of the four replications were sampled after 3 wk of UV-B treatment. Plant height, tiller number, leaf area, leaf dry weight, and culm dry weight were determined. Plant dry weight was the sum of leaf and culm dry weight. The differences between the treated plant and corresponding control were analyzed using LSD test. The ambient UV-B radiation of origin was calculated based on latitude, longitude, and growing season according to the Björn and Murphy model.

Dry matter change (%)

Dry matter change of 188 rice cultivars under enhanced UV-B radiation in the glasshouse compared with the UV-B level of their origin.

Rice cultivars used in this study showed a range of morphological changes and dry matter production to enhanced UV-B irradiation, although response varied among cultivars and groups (Table 1). About 28 of the test materials significantly reduced their leaf area, 32% significantly reduced their plant dry weight, and 76% significantly reduced their plant height. Indica and japonica groups did not differ much in plant height reduction. More reduction in tiller number (22%), leaf area (33%), and plant dry weight (34%), however, were observed in indicas than in japonicas under the UV-B treatment. Although the number of cultivars tested was small, the javanica rices now classified as tropical japonicas are more sensitive than temperate japonicas.

Because the ambient UV-B radiation level at lower latitudes is greater than that at higher latitudes, it is generally assumed that rice cultivars originating near the equator are more tolerant of UV-B radiation. The results of this study indicate that this hypothesis is not true.

The correlation ($r^2=0.01$) between dry matter changes under enhanced UV-B and ambient UV-B level at the site of origin was not significant (see figure). Even after removing the nine hybrid rice cultivars from the plot, the r^2 value was still nonsignificant.

Six rice cultivars with significantly increased biomass production under elevated UV-B did, however, originate from high UV-B areas (7-8 kJ/m² per d). DNJ164, DNJ46, and DNJ85 (aus rice) are grown in Bangladesh during summer, when UV-B levels are highest. Yunlen 19, Guze, and Musang A are indigenous to high elevation areas where prevailing UV-B irradiance is most likely high (see figure). The UV-B-tolerant cultivars evaluated in this study might be used as possible donors in a breeding program, but the genetic bases and makeup for their response differences must be further examined. ■

Stress tolerance—drought

Changes in water content of rice grain during water deficit

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Water content of cereal grains decreases during maturity. Environmental stresses such as extreme temperature or water deficit, however, may cause abrupt changes in grain water content and result in seed shriveling and discoloration, delayed ripening, and poor grain quality. Similarly, rapid reduction in water content of grains can result in poor seed germination and seed deterioration.

Five rice cultivars (AUS257, AUS196, UPLRi-7, IR43, and IRAT104) were seeded on several dates during the dry season under upland conditions with sprinkler irrigation. Plots were at different growth stages when a 12-d water deficit was imposed. Maximum water deficit was observed at the end of

the 12-d water deficit when $\psi_{panicle}$ was -0.8 MPa.

Panicle water potential was measured at dawn (0400-0600 h) using a pressure chamber. Developing grains were collected at 2- to 3-d intervals starting at 4-7 d after panicle emergence, and their water content and dry weights were determined gravimetrically. Rates of change were determined on the linear portion of dry weight and water content by least square method.

Grain dry weight, which generally followed a sigmoidal pattern, increased after panicle emergence regardless of water deficit; only slight differences in rates, however, were observed among most of the cultivars. During the panicle

Changes in grain dry weight (a) and water content (b) during water deficit.

